

Digital drug trading ecologies in context: Technological, geographic, and linguistic variation across darknet platforms

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ABSTRACT

Background: Previous research on darknet drug markets has primarily concentrated on large, English-language cryptomarkets, often overlooking regionally oriented platforms that operate in national languages. This study adopts a comparative, exploratory approach to examine how drug trade practices vary across linguistic, geographic, and technological contexts. We introduce the concept of “drug trading ecologies” to describe how platform features, communication norms, and localized settings together shape distinct trading environments.

Methods: Using a mixed-methods approach, we analyzed web-crawled data from three Tor-based platforms: Tsatti (Finnish-language chat), Cebulka (Polish-language forum), and Nemesis (English-language cryptomarket). Data were collected through customized web scraping and analyzed using statistical tools and qualitative content coding to examine platform-specific patterns. Our comparative approach highlights structural and localization-specific variations without attempting exhaustive conceptual definitions.

Results: Each platform displayed a distinct configuration shaped by its technical affordances and localization-specific user practices. Tsatti supported fast, hyperlocal, and highly anonymized exchanges with minimal user identity or community features. Cebulka enabled semi-public vendor-buyer interactions, trust-building through discourse, and diverse product bundling. Nemesis functioned as a transnational, professionalized cryptomarket with standardized listings, formalized trust mechanisms, and branding strategies.

Conclusions: Rather than attributing differences solely to local, transnational, or design factors in isolation, we argue that darknet drug trading ecologies emerge from the intersection of platform architecture, localization (geographic scope), and language. Our findings underscore the importance of considering these factors when conducting digital ethnography in illicit economies and providing concrete entry points for tailoring harm reduction interventions responsive to the diverse realities of online drug trading.

Introduction

Over the past decade, darknet has become an important channel for the trade of illegal narcotics, offering multiple types of platforms with distinct affordances and user logics that facilitate such activity (Martin et al., 2020). Accessible through specially configured software—most commonly the Tor browser (Tzanetakis, 2025)—these platforms have typically been associated with what Barratt and Aldridge (2016) define as cryptomarkets: e-commerce-like marketplaces that host multiple

vendors, enable anonymous transactions via cryptocurrency, and aggregate customer feedback. However, while prominent, cryptomarkets represent only one part of a broader online ecosystem of drug distribution (Haasio et al., 2024). Alongside them operate other forms of platforms, including forums (classical image/message boards) and localized chats, which support not only transactions but also discussions on drug culture, peer support, harm reduction, and the exchange of experience-based knowledge (Haasio et al., 2024).

Most existing research on darknet drug markets has focused on large,

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Fig. 1. Tsatti's interface (chat-based).

English-language cryptomarkets, such as Silk Road and its successors, which have shaped the dominant understanding of online drug trade practices (Barratt et al., 2014). These studies have provided valuable insights into transactional patterns, vendor strategies, and platform dynamics (Martin, 2014; Martin et al., 2020). However, such a focus often overlooks smaller, localized platforms operating in national languages, which can exhibit very different technical configurations, communication styles, and patterns of interaction. While the transnational nature of cryptomarkets facilitates international trade, local-language platforms embedded in specific cultural and linguistic contexts can offer a more nuanced view of how digital drug markets adapt to local needs, expectations, and social dynamics.

Against this backdrop, our study asks a simple yet underexplored question: how does drug trade vary across localized (and transnationalized) darknet platforms, and how are these variations shaped by the specific affordances and architectures of the platforms themselves? We focus on the specificities of regionally and linguistically embedded online sites and their socio-technical infrastructures. By examining three distinct platforms—the Finnish chat-based “Tsatti,” the Polish forum “Cebulka,” and the English-language cryptomarket “Nemesis”—we explore how the drug trade is shaped not only by technical features but also by local or transnational use. This allows us to move beyond aggregate patterns and open up a more grounded understanding of what we call drug trading ecologies. We avoid using the term “culture” in an essentialist or nationalized sense, aligning with long-standing critiques

that warn against treating culture as a bounded or homogeneous entity (e.g., Abu-Lughod, 1991; Hannerz, 1992). Instead, we refer to localization-specific trading ecologies—that is, socio-technical environments shaped by language, infrastructure, platform design, and geographic scope.

In the present article, we use this term not only to refer to what is being sold and how transactions are conducted, but also to the broader socio-technical practices, discourses, and identities that emerge around digital drug markets. These include aspects such as the ways in which trust is built or contested (Tzanetakis et al., 2016), how products are branded and described (Childs et al., 2020), how vendors position themselves (Siuda, 2024), and whether there is any discursive or relational interaction beyond pure transactions across a given platform (Siuda, 2025).

Although the selected platforms differed in format and scale, they all belonged to a broader category we refer to as darknet drug trading platforms. This term encompasses various types of online environments—cryptomarkets, forums, and chats—that facilitate the sale and exchange of illicit substances through anonymized infrastructures such as Tor. Rather than limiting our analysis to one subtype (e.g., cryptomarkets), we adopt this inclusive framing to highlight the diversity of platform ecologies while maintaining a coherent analytical lens.

Our understanding of drug trading ecologies draws inspiration from the concept of digital material culture, which emphasizes how digital infrastructures shape social practices and meanings. As Gehl (2018) has

Cebulka
Polish .onion forum

onion v3: cebulka7uxchnbpmqag5pfos4ngaxglsktzvha7a5rigndghvadeyd.onion

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Strony 1 2 3 ... 6 Następna

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Posty [1 do 25 z 139]

netrunner69

Cebulkowicz
Zarejestrowany: 2021-03-03
Posty: 188
Punkty handlu (?): 70
Oceny handlu: 377

2021-03-26 AM Ostatnio edytowany przez netrunner69 (Dzisiaj PM)

Temat: 🚀LSD🚀2cb🚀MDMA🚀RSO🚀weed🚀CARTY🚀amfa🚀koka🚀keta🚀changa🚀DMT🚀

Witaj w NETRUNNER CENTRAL 3.0

FOTO OFERTA CZYLI ZDJECIA TOWARU - LINK
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🚀 AKTUALNOŚCI:

- oferta aktualizowana CODZIENNIE
- skończyła się amfetamina - dostawa ok. 16.1
- jeśli nie uzyskałeś na swoje pytanie odpowiedzi na PW C lub WIRE lub WICKR.ME to znaczy, że odpowiedź znajdziesz w poniższym poście
- NOWY KOMUNIKATOR zamiast Wickre.me (który ma mieć wyłączoną aktywację nowych kont po nowym roku, a do końca 2023 zupełnie przestanie działać) - Wire. Mamy tam taki sam nick jak tutaj oraz na wickr - "netrunner69"
- na ten moment sprzedajemy LSD tylko od Gammagoblina, ponieważ tylko ten producent trzyma rewelacyjna i stała jakość
- jeśli zależy ci na czasie i chcesz szybkiej, bezpiecznej i sprawnej transakcji, to najlepszym wyborem na ten moment jest ESCROW (tylko i wyłącznie na cebuli) - takie zamówienia EKSPRES realizujemy CODZIENNIE
- mega stealth, jakość z labu, szybka wysyłka, hurtowe ceny & pozytywne oceny

🚀 SPIS TREŚCI:

1. FAQ
2. CENNIK AKTUALIZOWANY RAZ DZIENNIE
3. OPIS
4. JEŚLI CHCESZ KUPIĆ (WZÓR ZAMÓWIENIA)
5. KONTAKT

🚀 1. Najczęściej zadawane pytania:

Fig. 2. Cebulka's interface (forum).

argued, platforms are not neutral containers: they actively mediate what is visible, sayable, and doable within specific online environments. In the context of the darknet drug trade, this means that the architecture and affordances of particular platforms—such as the presence of rating systems, escrow mechanisms (buyer deposit funds into a third-party account, which are released only once the transaction is confirmed), or message boards—actively structure how drugs are described,

promoted, and exchanged. What might look like a simple post advertising MDMA, for example, is in fact embedded in a socio-technical framework that enables certain communicative norms (e.g., minimalism, coded language, references to purity) while discouraging others (e.g., open affective narratives). Thus, local (and meta-regional) drug trading ecologies are co-constituted by participant practices, and the technological affordances and constraints of the platforms they inhabit.

Another important aspect of drug trading ecologies is the way in which users position themselves—and are positioned—within these digital environments. Prior research has identified several recurring user categories, such as “psychonauts,” who approach drug use as a form of experimentation; recreational users, whose engagement is focused on pleasure, sociability, or leisure; and “self-care” users, who turn to substances as a means of managing physical or mental health challenges (Martin et al., 2020; Söderberg, 2016). These user types are not rigid classifications but rather emergent roles shaped by interactional practices, platform-specific discourse, and the framing of substances within localized contexts. Recognizing this diversity is essential for understanding how the drug trade on Tor reflects not just illicit transactions but also identity work and community-making. Overall, by comparing three linguistically and regionally distinct platforms, we aim to show how these ecologies differ and what implications such variation has for studying digitally mediated drug trade.

To explore local (and transnational) variations in online drug trading ecologies across technically different platforms, we adopt an exploratory comparative approach. Rather than testing a predefined hypothesis, we aim to identify and describe key dimensions of variation across the three studied platforms. Our methodology combines quantitative and qualitative analyses, drawing on web-crawled datasets from Tsatti, Cebulka, and Nemesis. These platforms differ not only in language but also in design and the presence or absence of community features. We focus on comparing them along selected dimensions: the range of substances sold, vendor specialization, trust-building practices, and the presence of discursive content beyond pure transactions. Throughout, we are careful not to treat regional context as an isolated explanatory factor. Instead, we examine how platform type and localization intersect to shape darknet drug trading ecologies. By doing so, we aim to provide a comparative basis for future studies examining how platform architecture and user localization interact in diverse darknet settings.

Methodology and data collection

We collected data from Tor-based darknet platforms using web scraping techniques tailored to each site’s architecture. The selected platforms—Tsatti, Cebulka, and Nemesis—were chosen based on several criteria. First, we prioritized active sites that showed signs of stability at the time of data collection. Given the volatility of darknet environments and the risk of sudden shutdowns due to law enforcement or community mistrust, platforms that had shown sustained user engagement were deemed more reliable sources of insight. At the time of writing (May 2025), Cebulka remains active¹. By contrast, Tsatti was taken down by law enforcement authorities in October 2024, and Nemesis had ceased operations following a shutdown in June 2024.

Second, the platforms differed in format and functionality (see Figs. 1–3). Tsatti functioned as a chat-based environment organized around geographic regions in Finland; Cebulka was a forum-style platform with threads dedicated to vendor offers and user discussions; Nemesis—being a cryptomarket—combined the features of a marketplace and a vendor-review system, with publicly accessible listings and embedded feedback mechanisms. From a qualitative perspective, each platform offered a markedly different environment: Tsatti was fast, minimalistic, and hyperlocal; Cebulka, semi-public, relational, and discourse-rich; and Nemesis, structured, transactional, and commercialized. These contextual differences shaped not only how data could be collected and analyzed, but also how trust, visibility, and community were expressed. While direct comparison is inevitably constrained by the platforms’ divergent affordances, we aimed to examine how platform infrastructures and localization-specific user practices shape the expression and structure of drug trading practices.

¹ Cebulka’s active URL as of May 2025 is <http://cebulka7uxchnbpvmqag5pfos4ngaxglsktzvha7a5rigrndghvadeyd.onion/>.

The collected datasets from the three platforms differed in format, scale, and structure. Below, we provide a summary of the collected material²:

1. Finnish dataset: 1574 messages from the Finnish onion website Tsatti, of which 977 were drug-related. We collected these in November and December of 2022. There were several messages on one page, and an automated web crawler accessed the website daily to collect the text content. Our extraction process collected and added the new individual messages from the crawled pages.
2. Polish dataset: 965 advertisement threads from the Cebulka onion website in January 2023. The threads were associated with the illicit drug trade. In this context, one thread page corresponded to a single selling advertisement message and its associated responses. An automated web crawler accessed the website once a day to collect the text content, converting text/HTML to plain text representations and removing duplicates.
3. English dataset: Nemesis data consisted of 1334 pages (files), of which 607 were drug-related. We collected these pages in December 2022. In this context, one page corresponded to a single selling advertisement message. We created a random sample from the pages to ensure that our sample size was similar to those in the other languages. We utilized an automated crawler to process web pages in plain text, focusing solely on selecting pages that sold products or services, while avoiding the collection of other pages, since this distinction was made possible by the URL scheme.

Given the technical and functional differences between the platforms, we summarize the key parameters of each dataset in Table 1 below. It includes core metadata and highlights whether interactional or non-transactional content was present in the dataset—an important indicator of discursive complexity and community presence. This comparative overview serves both as a reference point for the findings presented in the following sections and as a way to foreground the methodological constraints and affordances shaping our analysis.

The data collection strategy applied aligned with our aim of capturing platform-specific and localization-specific patterns, rather than building fully representative samples for generalization. Automated crawlers collected the web content from the three websites using pre-defined parameters. Importantly, we manually defined which parts of the websites to crawl by specifying the relevant URL structures. This human-guided selection, based on direct browsing and reading of each platform’s structure, is what we refer to as “functionally equivalent to a manual, human-level reading.”

This approach aligned with recent ethical guidelines on online trace data research (Harviainen et al., 2021) and mitigated potential ethical risks, while maintaining the integrity of both the research and the subject’s privacy. All described data collection and analysis procedures received ethical approval from two Institutional Review Boards: the School of Social and Political Science at the University of Edinburgh (ID: 288628) and the Faculty of Cultural Studies at Kazimierz Wielki University in Bydgoszcz, Poland. Importantly, in the case of Cebulka, we obtained explicit permission from site administrators to analyze the

² We employed darknet crawling as a well-established data collection method rooted in foundational studies such as Christin’s analysis of the original Silk Road in 2013 (Christin, 2013), which demonstrated the feasibility of systematically capturing anonymized illicit trade data. This approach was later reinforced by empirical mappings of Tor onion services (Owen & Savage, 2016) and, similar to ours, structured crawling techniques focusing on repeatable sampling methods, as well as selective data collection of commercial sections of onion marketplaces (Portnoff et al., 2017).

Fig. 3. Nemesis’s interface (cryptomarket).

Table 1
Comparative overview of the three analyzed darknet platforms.

Parameter	Tsatti	Cebulka	Nemesis
Platform type	Chat (region-based)	Forum	Marketplace; forum elements
Date of data collection	Nov–Dec 2022	January 2023	1–11 January 2023
Data structure	Short messages (ephemeral)	Threads with comments	Structured listings and reviews
Number of posts/threads	1574 messages (977 drug-related)	965 threads	1334 files (607 drug-related)
Number of vendors (approx.)	358 handles/Session IDs	165 unique vendor handles	212 vendor names
Data extraction method	Web scraping; html2text; RegEx (Python)	Web scraping, MaxQDA coding	Web scraping; Tidyverse (R); MaxQDA
Cultural/non-transactional content	Minimal	Moderate to rich (in some threads)	Mixed; mostly reviews, limited discussion
Drug types covered	Broad range; region-specific variation	Broad; many prescription drugs	Very broad; meta-regional focus
Geographic specificity	High (by region)	Low (no city-level data)	Medium (shipping from/to info)

content for academic purposes³.

The resulting corpora were processed and analyzed using a combination of descriptive statistical analyses in R and qualitative methods, including regular expressions, text mining in R, categorical coding in MaxQDA, and manual content analysis. These analyses were adapted to the specific technical and linguistic structures of each platform, with particular attention to how platform affordances and localization-

³ This permission was the outcome of a multi-stage ethnographic engagement conducted by the Polish part of the research team as part of a larger project (supported by the Polish National Science Centre, grant: 2021/43/B/HS6/00710), of which this article is one component. The process involved extended interaction, repeated ethical consultations, and the gradual establishment of trust through secure communication with the community administrators. While the full protocol cannot be reproduced in detail here due to space constraints, it is comprehensively documented in other publications (Siuda, 2025; Siuda, Świeca, Cheba, & Shi, 2024).

specific practices shaped communicative dynamics and transactional behavior. This mixed-methods approach allowed us to extract both structured information (e.g., drug categories, vendor counts, shipping methods) and semi-structured communicative content (e.g., expressions of trust, product branding, user identities). While the extraction tools varied depending on the platform’s interface and technical affordances, the guiding principle across all three cases was to capture both the transactional and interactional dimensions of the drug trade. By transactional dimensions, we refer to exchange-related aspects, such as sales, pricing, shipping, and escrow practices. By interactional dimensions, we mean communication-related aspects, including trust-building discourse (e.g., storytelling based on vendors’ personal experiences, recognition between vendors and clients), and broader community interaction.

When it comes to the content analysis (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005), coding procedures and category structures varied depending on the communicative and technical features of the sites. For Nemesis and Cebulka, we applied an inductive thematic coding approach using MaxQDA. After initial reading, recurring concepts were labeled and grouped into hierarchical structures. The coding schemes included multiple subcategories, which were then grouped into main categories, such as substances (drug types), transactional and interactional dimensions, logistics, business practices, product information, etc. The full coding schemes and category hierarchies are included in the Supplementary file (Part 1, Tables SF1–SF2). Importantly, the unit of analysis in the coding varied across platforms, reflecting their different technical structures: in Cebulka, threads (advertisement posts and responses) were coded; in Nemesis, individual vendor listings (files/pages) were coded; and in Tsatti, single chat messages were coded. This ensured that our analysis consistently focused on the core transactional unit of each platform, even though the exact form of an “offer” differed (thread, listing, or message). In the case of the Tsatti, the chat-based architecture, sparse content structure, and brevity of posts resulted in fewer thematic layers, and the interpretation leaned heavily on close contextual reading rather than elaborate categorization. However, the whole coding scheme is included in the Supplementary file (Part 1, Tables SF3).

This tiered approach enabled us to adjust the granularity of coding to the platform’s affordances, while still allowing for comparative insights across cases. We also report frequency-based summaries of crucial coded categories in the Results section. At the same time, we remain cautious not to overinterpret differences as stemming solely from national or cultural origin, and instead examine how localization and platform architecture co-construct communicative patterns.

Like many studies involving digital trace data, this project encountered certain limitations. First, we collected the datasets at slightly different time points, as previously mentioned. While all platforms were active during data collection, the asynchronous timing might have affected the comparability of activity levels and content patterns.

Second, as mentioned, the interfaces and data structures of the platforms varied considerably. Tsatti messages were ephemeral and automatically deleted after a certain period, meaning only a snapshot of the activity was captured. Cebulka, in contrast, has maintained persistent forum threads but did not include structured metadata such as the number of views or sales. Nemesis provided a more structured dataset, with product attributes, ratings, and review data readily extractable. These technical differences required tailored extraction and analysis strategies and also limited the extent to which all variables could have been compared across platforms. Comparing distinct digital environments such as chats, forums, and cryptomarkets inevitably involves methodological challenges, as each platform’s affordances and data structures shape what can and cannot be compared directly. Moreover, we recognize that differences in platform type are entangled with differences in language and geographic scope, making it analytically difficult to isolate any one factor. Our approach embraces this entanglement as a meaningful feature of the darknet drug trade.

Third, the depth and richness of available data varied across platforms. While Cebulka, for instance, included rich commentary and communal interactions, Tsatti was dominated by brief announcements, and Nemesis data was heavily shaped by the marketplace template. These differences affected the interpretability of findings and should be considered when drawing cross-platform comparisons.

Results

The following section presents our comparative findings along several thematic dimensions, including substances, vendor strategies, product descriptions, trust-building mechanisms, vendor presence and style, marketing and incentives, community interaction, geographic scope, and language. For ease of reference, Table 2, which summarizes these themes across all three platforms, is provided at the end of the Results section.

What is being sold and how?

Substances

A key entry point for comparing the three platforms was the range and prominence of different types of substances being sold, as reflected in their platform-specific listing patterns and structuring of product offers. While all sites offered access to a broad variety of drugs, the categorization and framing of these substances varied across platforms⁴. This section highlights both dominant classes (e.g., cannabis, opioids, prescription drugs) and specific substances. As our analysis is based on publicly visible advertisements, it captures the substances offered, not confirmed transactions.

On Tsatti (Finland), the most frequently advertised substances were prescription drugs (386 messages), followed by cannabis (299), opioids (268), amphetamines (198), MDMA (167), and mushrooms (79). The prevalence of prescription drugs and opioids reflected broader trends in the Finnish drug scene, where pain-relief-oriented substances are prominent (Keto et al., 2022). In contrast, Cebulka (Poland) showed a slightly different profile. Based on thread-level analysis, the most commonly mentioned substances included cannabis (172 threads), prescription drugs (48), MDMA (69), cocaine (55), and amphetamine

⁴ Categorization of substances was developed inductively by the research team, but followed the language, bundling patterns, and naming conventions used by vendors on each platform. We aimed to reflect the internal (emic) logic of each site while enabling consistent cross-platform comparison.

Table 2
Comparative synthesis of case-study findings.

Category	Tsatti	Cebulka	Nemesis
Substances	Prescription drugs and cannabis dominant; opioids, amphetamines, MDMA secondary; reflects Finnish demand	Cannabis and prescription drugs most common; heavy bundling (1200+ offers in threads)	Very broad range, including niche substances; vendor branding and optimization shape visibility
Vendor strategies	High specialization (71 % offer only one substance); compartmentalized	Flexible; bundling across categories (benzos, stimulants, psychedelics); co-occurrence networks show synergies	Split between specialists and generalists; branding, “combo packs,” upselling, and international reach
Descriptions and purity claims	Minimal: short posts, vague claims (“good stuff”); no lab testing	Pragmatic: sensory descriptions, effects, country of origin; little verification	Professionalized: purity %, lab tests, reagent results, dosage guidelines; harm reduction info present
Trust and reputation mechanisms (escrow, reviews, and refund)	Minimal: no reviews or ratings; ephemeral “fast trust” based on repeat encounters	Interpersonal trust: comments, forum dialogue, procedural fairness; escrow	Formalized: escrow, reviews, ratings, shipping guarantees, refund policies; e-commerce logic
Vendor presence and style	Highly anonymized; product plus quantity plus contact handle	Individualized: personal tone, self-disclosure, “ethics of care” narratives	Branded: vendor teams, professional tone, reputation scores, corporate style
Marketing and incentives	Almost none; brief functional posts	Personalized: free shipping, discounts, storytelling	Structured: discounts, samples, “customer service,” safety rhetoric
Community dynamics	Absent; purely transactional	Hybrid: mix of transactions and community-like interaction, advice sharing, harm reduction tips	Minimal: short reviews, limited dialogue; identity through scores and vendor names
Scale and geography	Hyperlocal; city- and region-specific	Domestic (Poland); national parcel lockers, domestic couriers	Transnational but clustered in W. Europe, UK, N. America; structured shipping routes
Language as boundary	Finnish, i.e., linguistic gatekeeping	Polish, i.e., domestic frame	English, i.e., lingua franca; meta-regional norms (tags, disclaimers)

(53). Notably, the platform featured a high number of offers per thread, especially in the case of prescription drugs (over 1200 individual offers), suggesting a practice of bundling goods and promoting larger inventories per vendor. This forum-based structure encouraged more sustained visibility of offers and the possibility for threaded discussions with buyers.

For Nemesis, vendors listed a wide variety of cannabis products (160 files), psychedelics (LSD [66]), MDMA (87), opioids (105), dissociatives (ketamine; 60), stimulants (e.g., cocaine [55]/amphetamine [53]), and prescription drugs (63). Unlike the more linguistically and geographically bounded Tsatti and Cebulka, Nemesis functioned as a highly professionalized, transnational marketplace, where drug visibility was shaped less by local demand and more by commercial logics, vendor branding strategies, and platform optimization. The prominence of niche substances (see the Nemesis coding structure in Supplementary file Part 1) and detailed product descriptions (“Product Information” category [326]) further reflected the influence of competition and

reputation-building in an international environment. These differences in substance visibility should be interpreted as platform-mediated expressions of supply, shaped by both vendor specialization and the way each platform organizes listings, not solely by local preferences.

Vendor strategies: specialization and bundling

An important feature of the analyzed darknet drug sites was how vendors structured their offerings—whether by focusing on a single substance, bundling products, or positioning themselves as versatile providers (Andrei & Veltri, 2024). Since this section focuses on how vendors grouped substances, it occasionally highlights less frequently listed drugs when their bundling patterns were analytically significant.

On Tsatti, specialization was the dominant pattern. 71 % of vendors offered only one substance, with minimal overlap. This suggested a relatively compartmentalized market where vendors built their identity around a particular substance and where buyers may have associated sellers with specific products or effects. These patterns also reflect the minimal structure of Tsatti, which constrained how offers could be organized and promoted.

On Nemesis, vendors typically followed one of two distinct strategies. Some built their brand around a single drug family (e.g., psychedelics), using specialization as a deliberate branding tool to differentiate themselves in a crowded, competitive market. Others positioned themselves as full-service providers, offering a broad range of substances, with transnational shipping options (607) and detailed product documentation (326). These generalist vendors included “combo packs,” trial assortments, or discounted bundles featuring both mainstream and niche substances (see “Sales” category [79]). For example, a seller might have offered MDMA together with LSD microdoses or included a free sample of a stimulant with a psychedelic purchase. These bundling strategies were commercially oriented, aimed at upselling, cross-promotion, and customer retention, and were often reinforced by review-driven feedback mechanisms (114).

Cebulka presented a more flexible model. While some vendors stuck to specific categories (especially prescription drugs or cannabis), many have used forum threads to bundle diverse products—e.g., benzodiazepines, stimulants, and psychedelics—in a single thread (Fig. 4). This bundling was often strategic, enabling vendors to increase visibility and reach multiple user niches. Co-occurrence analysis (Fig. 4) shows both niche segmentation and intentional synergies. Combinations such as

amphetamines and MDMA, or designer drugs with ketamine, did appear more frequently. This indicated an awareness of complementary effects or user interest in poly-drug experiences, which may have shaped how vendors bundled offers and framed their messaging.

To visualize overarching patterns in how substances are offered together on Cebulka, we generated a co-occurrence network based on vendor listings (Fig. 4). This network was created using Gephi, with nodes representing individual substances and edges indicating that two substances were co-listed by the same vendor. The size of each node reflected its overall frequency, while edge thickness corresponded to the relative strength of co-occurrence. Importantly, unconnected nodes represented substances that were typically offered alone, without significant pairing with other drugs (their isolated position in the network signaled lack of correlation; see the Supplementary file, Part 2, Table SF4, for all correlations). The aim of the graph was not to capture precise transactional volumes but to provide a relational overview of bundling trends and substance combinations.

Across platforms, then, vendor strategies ranged from narrow and functionally anonymous (Tsatti) to interactive and adaptive (Cebulka) to market-optimized and professionally branded (Nemesis). The way drugs were grouped, separated, or framed within each platform reflected distinct market ecologies, vendor roles, and interface-specific constraints, as well as assumptions about how substances were selected, combined, and consumed within localized trading contexts.

Substance descriptions and purity claims

Beyond the type and combination of substances offered, darknet platforms differed markedly in how drugs were described and framed by vendors. These descriptions were not merely practical; they also reflected broader norms and platform-specific expectations regarding credibility, expertise, and harm reduction.

On Tsatti, substance descriptions were minimal. Posts were typically short and to the point, often limited to the name of the drug, quantity, and a contact handle (322). Mentions of quality, including purity [140], or supposed effects (25) were generally vague (e.g., “good stuff” or “fast delivery”). There was no evidence of laboratory testing or detailed compositional data, which aligned with the platform’s emphasis on rapid, localized transactions rather than brand-building or risk management. This minimalist style can be seen as a result of Tsatti’s limited affordances, which did not encourage elaborate self-presentation or

Fig. 4. Co-occurrence networks of vendor-listed substances on Cebulka.

product differentiation.

In contrast, vendors on Cebulka were more likely to include sensory descriptions (e.g., taste, smell, structure) (120), and references to effects (e.g., “relaxing,” “mild trip”) (119) or country of origin (70). However, mentions of lab verification or chemical composition remained uncommon. The focus tended to be on the pragmatic and experiential qualities of the product rather than “scientific” certification (see “Communication with the Vendor” and “Community” categories).

On Nemesis, lab testing, purity percentages, and chemical breakdowns were frequent features of product listings (see “Product Information” category). Vendors often referred to reagent tests, black light results, or independent lab verification (188), particularly in the case of high-risk substances like MDMA, fentanyl analogues, or LSD. These descriptions were sometimes paired with harm reduction guidance (e.g., recommended dosage, warnings about mixing, onset and duration of effects) (221), which served a dual purpose: enhancing user safety and building vendor credibility. Nemesis vendors tended to adopt a more “professionalized” language, closer to that of the pharmaceutical or supplement industries. Purity, in this context, became both a technical and symbolic asset: a marker of quality, safety, and commercial legitimacy. Taken together, these framing strategies were not universal but highly dependent on how each platform allowed or encouraged extended descriptions, identity signaling, and professionalized language.

Building trust and community, performing reputation

Escrow, reviews, and refunds: platform-based mechanisms

All three platforms relied—explicitly or implicitly—on mechanisms of mediated trust. On Nemesis, these mechanisms were highly formalized and platform-integrated. Cryptocurrency-based escrow was a standard feature, and listings included vendor names with ratings and number of sales (607), reviews (114), shipping guarantees (44; see “Shipping Information” category), and refund policies (499). These features were comparable to e-commerce marketplaces and reinforced a performance of professionalism. For example, vendors frequently framed themselves as customer-oriented businesses (“Customer Service” category [110]): *We ship every order with the highest care... If a sending is lost and we believe you, it gets reshipped* (Nemesis, 01104). Refund policies on Nemesis were tiered, offering full refunds for regular customers, partial ones for others, or none at all in cases of unverifiable complaints.

On Cebulka, formal mechanisms like escrow were present, but were less central to vendor practices. Instead, trust was negotiated more interpersonally, often through public commentary and vendor-client familiarity (see “Community” category). Vendors included reminders like: *If you think what you received is of poor quality... try to prove it in any way possible. Usually, a test for just a few zlotys is enough to have a basis for a claim* (Cebulka, 00249). This put more responsibility on buyers while establishing a sense of procedural fairness. Unlike Nemesis, where reviews and stars dominated, Cebulka cultivated trust through ongoing dialogue and visibility over time. This was facilitated by the forum architecture, which supported persistent threads, user recognition, and interaction histories.

In comparison, Tsatti operated with minimal formal or informal trust infrastructure. There were no platform-level trust indicators such as reviews or ratings, and posts were typically ephemeral, brief, and focused on transactional coordination (see “Location” category) or basic trust signals such as a promise of a stress-free transaction (109). Trust was neither institutionalized nor explicitly performed; it appeared to rely on short-term risk calculation, repeated interactions in localized threads, or possibly external forms of verification, e.g., via Session IDs (36). While Nemesis and Cebulka relied on escrow-cryptocurrency-based payments, Tsatti posts typically implied face-to-face cash exchanges (104), with payment arrangements discussed privately on encrypted messengers like Wickr (358) or Session (36) and referred to through local conventions (“normal rules of how it’s done”). As such,

Tsatti offered an example of a low-trust or fast-trust environment, where vendor credibility was inferred from frequency of appearance or regional familiarity rather than explicit reputation-building. Tsatti vendors appeared as functionally invisible actors—present only through transactional signs. These forms of low-visibility, ephemeral trust practices align with the constraints of Tsatti’s chat-based architecture, which did not enable persistent reputation-building or public evaluation.

From individuals to brands: styles of vendor presence

A major structural difference emerged in how vendors presented themselves across platforms. On Cebulka, most vendors acted as individuals, speaking in the first person and often referencing their own experiences with particular substances (31). Posts included expressions of self-identification (“I only sell clean stuff,” “I know all my regulars”) (20) and personalized replies to comments (see “Mentions of Interaction...” category [7]). Some vendors shared personal stories (15) to bolster credibility or moral positioning: *For many years, I’ve battled depression, and the substances I offer have helped me—still help me—find solid ground again* (Cebulka, 00351). Such narratives suggested an ethics of care and self-expertise, positioning the vendor not as an anonymous seller but as a peer, guide, or helper within the community.

In contrast, vendors on Nemesis operated under branded identities, positioning themselves as companies with long histories and hundreds (or thousands) of sales across multiple markets (see “Shipping Destinations” category). For instance: *Welcome to DrugStar your professional drugstore. Active before on Agora... DREAMMARKET 7000 SALES 4.8+* (Nemesis, 00369). As already mentioned, they emphasized volume, satisfaction ratings, testing protocols, and logistical efficiency. Some adopted a near-corporate tone: *Our team hope to have good relationships in this market...* (Nemesis, 00017). This shift from relational trust to performance-based legitimacy marked a key distinction between platforms like Cebulka and Nemesis.

Conversely, vendor presence was stripped down to a minimum on Tsatti. Posts were limited to a short product label, a quantity, and a contact handle (e.g., Wickr or Session ID). Vendors did not use fixed usernames or branding or include personal or narrative content. This resulted in a highly anonymized, transient style of presence, as mentioned previously. Overall, we interpret these differences not as cultural preferences for trust models but as reflections of how different technical architectures structure visibility, memory, and accountability.

Marketing strategies: discounts, samples, and storytelling

Across the platforms, vendors deployed various strategies to attract and retain customers, ranging from material incentives to narrative positioning. On Nemesis, sellers emphasized professionalism and customer service through price and quality (52), resales, samples or discounts (29), and structured refund policies (499). These offers were complemented by safety rhetoric (“stealth packaging,” “no tracked shipping”).

On Cebulka, marketing was similar but often more personalized. Vendors referred to buyers by name (7), offering free shipping (8), samples (12), or loyalty-based discounts (49), and in some cases, using storytelling as a trust-building tool (15) (Siuda, Świeca, Cheba, & Shi, 2024). For instance, one vendor presented their selection as ethically curated: *I consciously exclude amphetamines, cocaine... I focus on socially harmless substances with minimal overdose risk* (Cebulka, 00351). Such narrative positioning was made possible by the forum structure, which enabled extended posts, replies, and direct address—elements absent from Tsatti and formalized on Nemesis.

Tsatti showed little evidence of marketing beyond basic product info. Messages were typically brief and functional, e.g., giving price information (289) or supposed effects (25), with no promotions, narrative elements, or incentives. This minimalist style reflected Tsatti’s low-interaction, regionally localized, and highly anonymized trading environment.

Community or commerce? Discursive interaction and social dynamics

While all analyzed platforms were primarily transactional in nature, they varied in terms of discursive interaction, peer engagement, and community-like dynamics, expressed through discussion threads, advice sharing, and symbolic performances of identity (Siuda, 2024, 2025).

On Tsatti, the social dimension was almost entirely absent. While earlier Finnish darknet forums were known for rich discussion on drug effects, experiences, and even harm reduction (Haasio et al., 2020), Tsatti has become a purely transactional space. Posts were brief, ephemeral, and focused on logistics: product, quantity, location (“Expression of Interest in Buying a Drug” [166]). Personal narratives and community interaction were nearly nonexistent, and there were no threads dedicated to broader conversation, with only sparse offers of help in using drugs (11). This structure suggested a shift toward efficiency and discretion, possibly reflecting heightened risk sensitivity or evolving user norms.

Conversely, Cebulka maintained a hybrid format, functioning both as a drug market and a semi-public forum. While the majority of threads were oriented toward transactions, the platform included visible traces of community life. Users gave advice (19), suggested improvements to the site (12), and recognized each other by username (7). These dynamics reflected the affordances of the forum format, which allows continuity of presence, shared memory, and the negotiation of mutual roles over time. In some cases, vendors even shared guides on safe use, synthesis, or testing (19), and framed themselves as experts or educators (20), not just dealers: *I am currently developing a guide for overcoming depression, which I will share on Cebulka... distilled from years of trying various treatments* (Cebulka, 00351). Although such content remained secondary, its presence revealed that Cebulka supported a layer of mutual recognition, belonging, and negotiations, especially among long-term users.

Nemesis represented a commodified and individualized environment. While there was limited user interaction in the form of reviews and comments (114), these were usually short, product-focused, and tied to transactional feedback (“arrived fast,” “weak effect,” “scam”). Vendors may have positioned themselves as professionals (see “Customer Interaction” category) or harm reduction-aware (108), but this was done through static content (product descriptions, refund policies) rather than conversation. *Please practice proper safety measures and start small!* (Nemesis, 01148). There was little space for open-ended dialogue or community-building, and user identity was primarily constructed through numerical reputation ratings, sales count, and satisfaction scores alongside vendor names (607).

Platform scale, geographic targeting, and transactional reach

Local platforms, meta-regional market: scale and orientation

The scope of darknet drug markets varied not only by product range or user base but also by scale of operation, geographic targeting, and the linguistic boundaries of each platform. Tsatti and Cebulka were predominantly regional in scope, both in terms of user language and presumed geographic coverage. Tsatti was segmented into regional subforums corresponding to Finnish towns and cities (67). Although some vendors posted in multiple threads, 64 % operated in only one geographic area, reinforcing their hyperlocal character.

Similarly, Cebulka functioned in Polish and targeted a domestic audience. While specific delivery regions were not mentioned, the structure and content of threads suggested a shared linguistic and regional frame, oriented toward users familiar with Polish contexts, logistics, and payment systems.

By contrast, Nemesis was explicitly transnational. However, rather than being truly global in scope, its user base and shipment patterns were concentrated around a few major regions—particularly Western Europe, the UK, and North America (see “Shipping Destinations” category). Thus, it operates across national borders but remains anchored in specific transnational clusters. Listings were typically in English, and vendors offered international shipping options, often with dropdown

menus for “Ship from” and “Ship to.”

Market logics, routes of delivery: domestic vs. international flow

The distinction between local and transnational platforms was further evident in shipping routes. On Tsatti, transactions happen within cities or regions, with physical proximity used as a proxy for trust. Vendor location was often city-specific (67), and products were advertised for pickup or drop-off in places like Helsinki, Vantaa, or Tampere. Messages often referenced local meet-ups or drop locations within urban zones (74).

On Cebulka, vendors used national parcel lockers (e.g., InPost), the Polish Post, or domestic courier services (see “Shipping Method” category [258]). International shipping was absent, and delivery instructions were often informal and flexible—negotiated in thread comments or via encrypted messengers (see “Communication with the Vendor” category [270]).

In comparison, Nemesis supported an extensive network of transnational shipments. The platform offered detailed metadata for each post: origin country, destination region (see “Logistics” categories), shipping methods (602), refund policies (499), and similar. The data revealed structured shipping routes by substance type, with certain drug classes (e.g., benzos) showing higher international flow than others (e.g., cannabis concentrates). Fig. 5 shows that different substances originated from specific hubs: cannabis from the UK and Spain, psychedelics from the Netherlands and the US, and benzos and opioids from Germany and the UK. This structuring of routes by substance type suggested established logistical pipelines within the dark economy. These geographic patterns influenced availability, risk levels, pricing, and delivery times.

Language as a boundary: filtering locality

Language also functioned as a powerful filter of access and identity. Tsatti and Cebulka, by virtue of their Finnish and Polish interfaces, effectively gatekept participation. These linguistic boundaries acted not as cultural barriers per se, but as practical filters tied to language fluency, communication style, and expectations embedded in local infrastructures. While anonymity was core to darknet practice, linguistic familiarity became an entry ticket, shaping who participates and how. On the other hand, Nemesis leveraged English as a lingua franca. This enabled wider participation and scaled the market beyond national boundaries, but it also required sellers to adhere to certain meta-regional norms: clear formatting, standardized tags, multilingual disclaimers, etc. Thus, language served not only communicative but also boundary-making functions, structuring inclusion, exclusion, and expected behaviors.***

Table 2 synthesizes the main findings across the three platforms, highlighting how their technical architectures, linguistic boundaries, and market orientations structured drug trading practices. This comparative view underscores that substance visibility, vendor strategies, trust mechanisms, and community dynamics, among others, are mediated by platform-specific environments (*drug trading ecologies*).

Discussion

This exploratory and comparative study reveals differences between the three darknet platforms—Tsatti, Cebulka, and Nemesis—in how platform architecture, language use, and geographic embeddedness co-shape practices of drug distribution, presentation, and trust, among others. While all three sites facilitated illicit transactions, they differed in how they structured transactions, communicated value, and fostered trust or community. Tsatti (chat) resembled ephemeral, street-level dealing with minimal branding and quick local exchanges; Cebulka’s forum affordances enabled semi-public negotiation and relational trust; and Nemesis reflected a cryptomarket model with standardized listings, escrow, and branded vendor identities. We interpret these dynamics not as culturally predetermined, but as outcomes of affordances and communication modalities enabled by each platform. Language acted both as a communicative medium and as a filter, structuring who

Fig. 5. Trading route visualization from Nemesis—Top 5 routes for selected substances.

participates and how norms are reinforced. At the same time, whether a platform was locally embedded (as in Tsatti and Cebulka) or meta-regional in orientation (as in Nemesis) influenced visibility, logistics, and how the structural features were taken up and negotiated. Together, all these elements configure distinct platform-specific drug trading ecologies.

Our findings suggest that the distinction between local and meta-regional is not entirely clear-cut. Although Nemesis was structured as a transnational, English-language cryptomarket, its user base may have included buyers and sellers who operated primarily within national or regional contexts, particularly in the UK, which emerged as a key node in our shipping data. This highlights the need for a more nuanced understanding of “locality,” accounting not only for language but also for actual usage patterns and embeddedness within national infrastructures. In this sense, even so-called transnational markets can function as locally meaningful spaces for certain user groups. As Demant et al. (2018) describe, this is a case of “going local on a global platform,” where buyers’ preferences for safety, risk, and convenience intersect with structural limitations. This view resonates with studies by Norbutas (2018) and Van Buskirk et al. (2016), which show that, despite their technical openness to global trade, cryptomarkets tend to remain geographically clustered. Composition of cryptomarket listings can

differ across countries (Van Buskirk et al., 2016), and buyers often prefer domestic transactions, avoiding international orders due to higher risks, longer delivery times, and increased chances of interception (Norbutas, 2018). Tzanetakis (2018) observed that despite their transnational infrastructure, cryptomarkets often reflect regional differences in supply structures and user behaviors. This suggests that what appears as a global infrastructure may function as a constellation of regional sub-markets. Our findings confirm this pattern, while also illustrating how interactional discourses and technological affordances may co-shape the differences between these regional submarkets. This echoes Craciunescu and South’s (2023) argument that digital drug markets are embedded in broader drug cultures, including subcultural rituals and perceptions of risk. In our data, this was evident on Polish and Finnish platforms, which encouraged informal exchanges and risk negotiation practices distinct from those seen on Nemesis.

At the same time, our analysis supports arguments by Tzanetakis and Marx (2023) that cryptomarkets reflect platform capitalism, where value is extracted not only from commodities (in this case, drugs) but also from user data, behavioral patterns, and the systemic ambiguity between legality and illegality. Our findings resonate with this argument, particularly in the case of Nemesis, where the platform’s internal regulation, professionalized vendor practices, and reputation systems

mirror the service-oriented logic of platform economies. At the same time, our study extends these insights by showing how such logics are not universal: platforms like Cebulka and especially Tsatti follow different trajectories, with much less emphasis on service optimization and more reliance on informal norms or ephemeral trust. This highlights infrastructural heterogeneity across darknet platforms, while still acknowledging their embeddedness in broader platform dynamics.

Our findings also resonate with prior research on user typologies such as psychonauts, self-care users, or recreational consumers (Drumm et al., 2005; Móró et al., 2011), but we focus instead on the platform conditions under which such or similar identities become visible and performable. In particular, sites like Cebulka, which support interaction, discussion, and long-form expression, create space for users and vendors to narrate their roles, share experiences, and signal values. This opens up the potential for exploring user categories as emergent, socially performed identities embedded in discursive and relational practices. In contrast, more transactional platforms like Nemesis constrain such identity work to short, review-based formats, while sites like Tsatti, with its ephemeral, minimal structure, offer no space for interaction at all. This makes any nuanced understanding of user roles, motivations, or moral framings difficult—if not impossible—to extract. These contrasts highlight how platform design can enable or silence subjective dimensions of drug use and trade.

In addition, the comparative perspective and findings of this study have direct implications for drug policy and harm reduction strategies, which must be tailored not only to substance trends but to how substance use and exchange are mediated by local platform conditions, communication practices, and infrastructural constraints (Kelly et al., 1996). In particular, our findings suggest several concrete entry points for designing interventions that reflect the realities of digital drug trading ecologies. First, chat-based environments such as Tsatti illustrate that harm reduction in fast-trust, ephemeral markets cannot rely on persistent messaging but instead requires low-threshold, mobile, and time-sensitive interventions—e.g., short safety alerts or encrypted helplines designed for rapid consumption (echoing how cryptomarkets integrate advice directly at purchase points; see Aldridge et al., 2018). Second, forum-based spaces, such as Cebulka, demonstrate that semi-public discussions already support peer education and knowledge sharing. Here, harm reduction and drug policy strategies can build on existing user-generated content (e.g., guidance on dosage, safe combinations) by integrating verified resources or partnering with community moderators—a strategy consistent with studies emphasizing the expansion of harm reduction via forums (Davitadze et al., 2020) and the shaping of community identity around harm reduction norms (Gilles, 2025). Third, in professionalized cryptomarkets such as Nemesis, where escrow, reputation, and vendor branding dominate, policy interventions could leverage these formalized structures. For instance, interventions could promote the inclusion of drug-checking results or standardized harm reduction guidelines within vendor profiles. This approach aligns with evidence that anonymity and review systems can facilitate digital harm reduction (Gomes & Sultan, 2024), while acknowledging that cryptomarkets have only conditional, and limited, harm-minimizing effects (Sumnall, 2018).

While several limitations have already been acknowledged in the methodology section—such as differences in data structures across platforms and asynchronous scraping dates—other constraints also deserve further attention. First, our analysis is based entirely on publicly available textual data, which inevitably omits invisible forms of communication such as private messages and off-platform exchanges (Childs et al., 2020) that shape both trade and trust. Second, given the exploratory nature of this study, the data represent only snapshots in time and reflect the platforms as they existed during the specific collection periods. Third, although our analysis draws on three significant darknet platforms, this cannot fully capture the broader variety of existing sites. Importantly, even within English-language contexts, not all markets resemble Nemesis in being transactional and depersonalized.

As shown in Bancroft et al.'s (2020) study of the “PFM” market, English-language forums can also be community-oriented, trust-based environments focused on mutual support and shared values rather than purely commercial logic. Fourth, the inherent volatility of the darknet ecosystem further complicates longitudinal interpretation: at the time of writing, two of the three studied platforms have already ceased operation. However, this instability also highlights the value of our dataset. By analyzing persistent sites during their active phases, we provide much-needed baseline knowledge that can guide future research as new platforms emerge and evolve. Taken together, these limitations do not undermine the value of the findings but rather highlight the complexity and fluidity of the environments under study. They also point to the importance of remaining attentive to the diversity of darknet ecologies—technically and interactionally—when interpreting any snapshot of this shifting terrain.

This study has demonstrated that drug trading ecologies on the darknet vary significantly depending on platform design, language, and market orientation. Our exploratory and comparative approach reveals how deeply trading practices, trust mechanisms, and community life are embedded in these techno-social configurations. These findings call for a broadened analytical lens—one that moves beyond dominant English-language cryptomarket narratives and attends to the interplay between platform structure, linguistic accessibility, and regional specificity. We encourage researchers to continue exploring the darknet not only as a marketplace but as a space of evolving drug-related ecologies, particularly within smaller linguistic communities that remain under-represented in current scholarship.

Data availability

We publish three datasets freely available under a CC BY 4.0 license, allowing reuse and modification with attribution. The datasets can be accessed via Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15300503>. Each dataset corresponds to a different language-specific site: Finnish.zip—data from “Tsatti;” Polish.zip—data from “Cebulka;” English.zip—data from “Nemesis.” Each folder contains: JSON files of the webpages (machine-readable), screenshots of the websites, and readable text versions in the “textpages” folder.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.drugpo.2025.104984](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugpo.2025.104984).

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